

HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-08 – GA 101069492

Revolutionary energy storage cycle with carbon free aluminium

D7.1 Public Project Website

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Table of contents

Executive summary	5
Extensive summary	5
1. Website design and registration data.....	6
2. Website description	6
2.1 Home.....	6
2.2 Concept.....	8
2.3 Team	8
2.4 News & Events	9
2.5 Documents	10
2.6 Gallery	11
2.7 Cooperation.....	12
3. Cookies.....	12
4. Future work.....	12
5. Conclusion.....	13
Annex	13

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
RP	Report
D	Deliverable
T	Task
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

Executive summary

The deliverable D7.1 Public Project Website is a public document of the REVEAL project, delivered in the context of WP7 Dissemination and Exploitation, task T7.2 Website, logo and promotion material. This document presents an important step in the objective of developing and deploying the REVEAL project website, dedicated to a wide public audience all around the world. The website is not intended to be static. Especially the “News & Events”, “Gallery”, and “Documents” section will be once a month (or whenever needed) updated and managed by the Dissemination leader - FENIX based on the partner's inputs and project development.

Extensive summary

The deliverable D7.1 Public Project Website is a public document of the REVEAL project, delivered in the context of WP7 Dissemination and Exploitation, task T7.2 Website, logo and promotion material. The objective of task T7.2 is to secure the successful communication and dissemination through the implementation and deployment of a Communication and dissemination plan.

This document presents a step in the objective of developing and deploying the REVEAL project website, dedicated to a wide public audience all around the world. As a first step, the logo of the project, dictating the visual identity, was developed. Once that was ready, an entire project website was constructed utilizing the visual identity. The website is available online and can be accessed at www.reveal-storage.eu.

The website is not intended to be static. Especially the “News & Events”, “Gallery”, and “Documents” section will be once a month (or whenever needed) updated and managed by the Dissemination leader – FENIX, based on the partners’ inputs and project’s development. The design of the project website is planned to be updated minimum three times per project, reflecting the project’s main achievements, technical development, new videos, etc. Different audiences are being considered, it has been streamlined and presented in a way that is accessible by wide range of stakeholders. An initial version of REVEAL project website has been designed, provisioned, and deployed on the internet. The site is hosted by FENIX – WP7 leader, under the domain reveal-storage.eu.

Google Analytics as Key Performance Indicator (KPI) has been considered and deployed at this early stage of the project (e.g., views, users, countries, languages, browsers, device, etc.). Another KPI which will be tracked is the downloads from the project website (e.g., promo materials, deliverables, publications, newsletters, etc.). The website was designed considering display on different devices such as desktop, mobile or tablet.

1. Website design and registration data

The REVEAL project website has been created, under the www.reveal-storage.eu. Webhosting and domain were bought by FENIX. Under the Webhosting project info email “info@reveal-storage.eu” was created to be further used for social network profiles registration, newsletter campaign, etc. email is maintained by FENIX.

2. Website description

The website has been designed by FENIX and the main aim is to address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?

The website itself contains the following information:

- general information about the project
- partners details
- list of news and events
- all public material that is generated by the project
- links to social network profiles
- newsletter subscription
- contact information
- gallery

2.1 Home

The “Home” page of the REVEAL website contains basic information about the project. The upper part of the screen shows the project’s logo, links for the social profiles and a navigation panel, using a structure that is commonly used. At the top of the page is the project’s title, short information about the project and links to other pages with more information. Next on the “Home” are the projects goals, news & events, links to articles the project has been featured in. At the bottom of the page are newsletter subscription, contact, links for the social profiles, and funding as shown in Figure 1.

REVEAL
CONCEPT TEAM NEWS & EVENTS RESOURCES COOPERATION

REVOLUTIONARY ENERGY STORAGE CYCLE WITH CARBON FREE ALUMINIUM

[Learn more](#)

ABOUT

CONCEPT

REVEAL project develops a new technical solution for storing large amounts of energy with an energy storage density of more than 15 MWh/m³ at low cost for the production of heat and electricity in winter.

Learn more

FUNDING

REVEAL is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme and Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).
DURATION: July 2022 - June 2026

View COORDIS

TEAM

Research consortium with nine partners from seven different European countries.

Meet the team

GOALS

SEASONAL ENERGY STORAGE CYCLE
development of breakthrough components and solutions that are needed for an Al electrochemical energy storage cycle

POWER-TO-AL (STORAGE CHARGING)
based on renewable electricity without emissions of greenhouse gases from the Al smelter (Power-to-Al) process

AL-TO-ENERGY (STORAGE DISCHARGING)
emission free Al-to-Energy

LIFE CYCLE AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS
for better economic and environmental performance

NEWS & EVENTS

READ MORE

KICK OFF PRESS RELEASE
Read our first official press release
14/11/2022

ARTICLE BY ICETEC
Article about REVEAL kick off on IceTec website
14/11/2022

KICK OFF MEETING
Our project has been officially "kicked off!"
14/11/2022

Interview with ARCTUS
Printed and online article by ARCTUS
14/11/2022

INDUSTRY DAY POSTER
The project poster has been presented during Industry Day at IPT / OST
14/11/2022

FEATURED IN

EE-NEWS.CH

OST: Mit Aluminium heizen - EU und Schweizer Forscher beschleunigen

SOLARSERVER.DE

Forschungsgemeinschaft untersucht Aluminium als Energiespeicher

PV-MAGAZINE.DE

Photovoltaik und Wasserstoff in Aluminium: Landflughafen speichert und zum Heizen nutzen

ENERGATE-MESSENGER.CH

Forschung aus der EU und der Schweiz greift ein alternatives Energiespeichersystem

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER.

Sign up with your email address to receive news and updates.

Contact: info@reveal-storage.eu

Sign up with your email address to receive news and updates.

Co-funded by the European Union

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FIGURE 1: REVEAL HOME PAGE

FIGURE 3 REVEAL TEAM PAGE

2.4 News & Events

This page presents a list of news and events, which will include all meetings of the project partners and important events in which a large group of the consortium partners participates, such as conferences, fairs, workshops as shown in Figure 4. Short info about the most relevant upcoming news is reflected on the “Home” page.

FIGURE 4 REVEAL NEWS & EVENTS PAGE

2.5 Documents

The “Documents” page is split into subsections Press releases & posters, Promo materials and Public deliverables as shown in Figure 5. Subsections can be added based on the project requirements at any time. The Documents page will contain all materials that has been published and is thus publicly available (respecting copyright issues).

FIGURE 5 REVEAL DOCUMENTS PAGE

2.6 Gallery

The “Documents” page displays images from meetings, events and shows pictures related to the project as shown in Figure 6.

FIGURE 6 REVEAL GALLERY PAGE

2.7 Cooperation

The “Cooperation” page is split into subsections Cluster projects and Associations as shown in Figure 7.

FIGURE 7 REVEAL COOPERATION PAGE

3. Cookies

Cookies are small text files stored on user’s computer by their browser. They have many applications, such as: tracking users as they navigate around a website; remembering user preferences; auto-logins for visitors coming back to a site; and website security. Within REVEAL project website cookies policy was also implemented.

4. Future work

Short-term improvements to the website under consideration at the time of deliverable writing include:

- update the website content based on the project progress annually
- adding demo site and videos page

- adding cooperation page in order to increase the visibility of cluster projects and initiate the cooperation
- in case of workshop organization by project or together with cluster projects, registration page and event info to be created

5. Conclusion

The online REVEAL website is a key element of the project’s dissemination and communication strategy. This site will ensure the visibility of the project, facilitate the diffusion of the project's results, and promote their exploitation.

An initial version of the REVEAL project website has been designed, provisioned and deployed on the internet. Currently consisting mostly of static content, it has been designed to answer the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have. The project website will continuously form and develop as the project itself grows.

The information included on the project website is likely to be valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, the consortium aims at ensuring that the website will continue to exist after the project funding has finished min 2 years and that bookmarks and published URLs will continue to function.

Annex

List of figures

Figure 1: REVEAL HOME PAGE	7
Figure 2 Reveal Concept Page	8
Figure 3 Reveal Team Page	9
Figure 4 Reveal News & Events Page.....	10
Figure 5 Reveal Documents Page.....	11
Figure 6 Reveal Gallery Page	11
Figure 7 Reveal Cooperation Page.....	12

